

DICTATION AS LANGUAGE LEARNING TOOL

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Abstract

This article describes some types of dictations with tasks how to use of them, analysis of the researchers who practiced some types of dictation,

Key words: dictation,activity,teaching tool,methodologist, improve, vocabulary, listening and writing skills, technique,text.

Introduction. Dictation has been used for language learning for several years. Dictation develop the students writing and listening skills.Ut not only enhance the writing and listening skills but also it enlarge a student's vocabulary and fills his mind with good standarts of speech. And,it is the most useful learning tool and widely used around the world.

In the nineteenth century was used extensively in teaching foreign language. As a teaching tool, it become more popular in foreign language teaching during the 1960's. But, most of the language instructors and methodologist considered this method as useless and out-of-date. Therefore, dictation rejected at the late nineteenth century. But, in the early years of the twentieth century, dictation regained popularity, especially as it provided high correlation with language proficiency. In any average group of European teachers more than half use dictation either regularly of from time to time in their teaching.(Davis and Rinvoluceri, 2002 ;21)

What is a dictation?Dictation is a method of teaching which a person tells a text and learners need to listen carefully and try to write the text without errors. In Longman Dictionary Of Applied Linguistics "dictation" is defined as a technique used in both language teaching and language testing in which a passage is read aloud to students or test takers with pause during which they must try to write down what they have hear as accurately as possible (2002)[p.157]

How to select a text for a dictation? Text which chosen for learners should be appropriate to the level of them. For example, If the learner's level is elementary, teachers should choose an easy text. There should not be complex words, conjunction and phrases in this text. Also, this text should be short. Words in this text should be between 80 and 100. Moreover, the teacher should stop

frequently during the recitation of the text because the student's level is elementary, they find it difficult to write quickly and as a result they make many mistakes. If the learner's level is upper-intermediate, teachers have to choose very difficult text. There should be a lot of complex vocabulary, phrases, conjunctions, and even idioms in this text. Text should not be short. Words in this text should be between 150 and 200. Also, the teacher should pause very little while reciting the text. Because the learner's level is high, and he or she can write fast without mistakes.

In addition, if teachers choose interesting texts for dictation, students will not be bored while writing the text. I think the history of the origin of something is very interesting for everyone as well as for students. Therefore, student should write many texts about history, because these texts are both interesting and students will have some knowledge about history.

In one word, a traditional dictation is when a teacher dictates and students listen and write down word by word. Noteworthily, teachers should select texts for dictations taking into account the level of their learners.

When we researched the theme dictation, we found out the following results that outstanding linguists' opinions on it: 1) Nation views dictation as having "listening input and written input (1991) [p.12] Thus, doing dictation activity fosters listening skill as "learners receive some spoken input" and develops writing skill as "learners write what they heard." He states that the learners' writing "is affected by their skill at listening."

2) Morris considers dictation "a means of encouraging correct spelling in any piece of writing work" as well as "a means of reinforcing structure and vocabulary" (1983) [p.125]. She believes that dictation is "a most useful tool in listening training "so that teachers might use it as one of their teaching techniques in class.

3) Likewise, Frodesen agrees that dictation enhances students' grammar, vocabulary, and writing. It is indeed an "effective way to familiarize students with the ways in which grammar and vocabulary interact in common collocation as well as to address errors in writing that may result in part from mismatches between learners' aural perception of English forms and standard English grammar and spelling" (2001)[p.243]

4) Norris who investigated Japanese university and college false beginners of English found that the implementation of creative dictation exercises (dialogue

dictation race , numbers dictation, pronunciation relay, building with rods, and picture dictation) in the students' English classes motivated the students “by providing practice in several areas (e.g. accuracy, fluency, self-correction, negotiation of meaning, etc) while combining the speaking, listening, writing, and reading skills” (1993) [pp.78-79]

5) Davis and Rinvoluceri are saying that “dictation of any kind provides a nice blend of listening, writing, and checking through reading” [p.79]

6)Alkire pointed out that dictation helps the development of “all four language skills in an integrative way.” It also “develops short-term memory”, provides students with “practice in correct forms of speech”, in note-taking, and in “comprehending and transcribing clear English prose”. In addition, it raises students and teacher's awareness of “the students' comprehension errors - phonological, grammatical, or both”, as well as spelling errors.(2015)[<http://itesj.org/Techniques/Alkire-Dictation.html>]

7) Finocchiaro mentions that “[dictation] ensures attentive listening; it trains pupils to distinguish sounds; it helps fix concepts of punctuation; it enables pupils to learn to transfer oral sounds to written symbols; it helps to develop aural comprehension; and it assists in self-evaluation.”(1969) [p.233-248]

Taking into account all viewpoints of scholars above we can conclude that dictations are very important for learner. When learners use dictation for learning four language skills, they learn easily. Moreover, using dictation to facilitate students memorizing English vocabulary also revealed that the dictation given to the students was an effective strategy which could improve the students' vocabulary and learning outcomes.

Dictation activities for teachers

There are various dictation activities that language teachers can use their class. Below are dictation activities that help develop student's phonics skills, grammar and vocabulary knowledge, and note-taking and writing skills.

1-activity.

This activity's name is fill in gaps. In this exercise, students are given a text and some words in the text are missed. Students have to fill the text with words that have been omitted by listening to the text through an audio or teacher. For example:

“Cinema and theatre

Cinema and theatre differ in For instance while theatre has been present since the earliest days of the antiquity. Cinema is a never form. Are some people who give their opinion and preferences to compare cinema and theatre. cinema is more popular,I prefer going to the theatre because it is more social and it's nice to see people wearing smart clothes and make up while waiting in the foyer. I hate it when people talk In the cinema, eat their pop corn and drink coke as if they are at home. But the people in the theatre are more I don't know why I can't see much between them and I can't say I like both of them. There is a big difference between cinema and theatre. Cinema is livelier, more active and colourful. The action is faster when compared to theatre. You don't just see actors and on the stage but lots of locations on Cinema uses technology a great deal and as far as I'm concerned cinema is number one.”

It is not necessary to miss any word in the text. The word should be omitted which is pronunciation should be similar to another word. For instance:”youngster”. Pronunciation of the word “youngster” is very similar to the word “young star”. In such cases, the learner should know the translation of these words in order to find the correct answer. As a result, learner's vocabulary increases very well.

Answer is the exercise: some ways, here, although, loudly, respectful, though, difference, infinitely, screen.

Similar vocabulary:

Some ways- subways. Although-allow

Here-hear. Loudly-lovely

Respectful-impactful. Though- thought

Difference-difderents. Infinity -infinity

Screen-scream

2-ACTIVITY

Second activity's name is Lyrics training. This activity releted with technology. Because, nowadays, it is impossible to imagine our life without technology. If teachers use technology during the lesson, pupils will not be bored with lessons.

Lyrics training is very interesting activity for learners. Firstly, learners should install program of Lyrics training. And, they should create their own account. Next, they choose a song. Learners listen music with subtitle. A word in the text of the music will be missed. Student complete the missing words or phrases a song. Lyrics training is the most exciting activity for improving listening and writing skills of learners.

3-ACTIVITY

Third activity's name is picture dictation. It uses to enhance the knowledge of grammar and vocabulary. In picture dictation, pupils are asked to listen to the audio or teacher and draw or complete a picture based on what they hear. For instance: teacher gives a picture of an empty classroom and pupils are asked to draw the location of some items in the classroom based on the text they hear. Such exercise allows pupils to learn vocabulary of things in classroom and language items of propositions of place.

4-ACTIVITY

This activity's name is vocabulary dictation. In this activity, students are given some vocabulary which this vocabulary is keywords. Using the keywords, students then discuss the ideas in groups and rewrite the text. Vocabulary dictation encourages students to work more creatively. Students see and hear only keywords or phrases of a listening text and using the keywords. They are asked to write a new text. This activity improves students writing skill and speech.

5-ACTIVITY

Next activity's name is number dictation. This activity is simple activity. Teachers tell numbers, students write this numbers with letters. This activity checks students reaction and improves critical thinking

Conclusion

All things considered that dictation can be accomplished not only to improve listening comprehension skills, but also to develop autonomy in learning as it provides learners with opportunities to perform their ability in various language skills and language aspects. Also, modern dictation activities are more interesting and beneficial than traditional dictation for language learners. Modern dictation activities are advised all level learners by linguists. Because, they are very exciting and activities show their effects quickly to learners.

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